

Titrimetric Microdetermination of Kaempferol from *Ipomoea fistulosa* Using Platinic Chloride as Oxidizing Agent in Acid Medium

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Kaempferol, isolated from the pink violet flowers of *Ipomoea fistulosa*, has been quantitatively determined in micro amounts by oxidising with platinic chloride in highly acidic medium. The reaction between kaempferol and platinic chloride in acid medium is completed at 28 equivalence resulting in the formation of formic acid as main oxidation product. Maximum error is $\pm 0.9\%$. The equilibrium of the reaction mixture is disturbed by heating directly or lowering the concentration of H-ions. The method is simple, accurate and reproducible.

UPTO date literature does not describe a simple method for the determination of kaempferol in acid medium isolated from natural sources. However, it has been determined polarographically¹; by counter current distribution method²; and by platinum(IV) chloride in alkaline medium³.

Kaempferol was isolated from pink violet flowers of *Ipomoea fistulosa* widely distributed in India. After isolating and purifying kaempferol it was necessary to find out an accurate but simple quantitative method for determining it. As such kaempferol ($C_{15}H_{10}O_6$) has a known structure with molecular weight 286.0.

Present work deals with the quantitative determination of kaempferol in micro amounts by oxidising with platinic chloride in highly acidic medium. The reaction between kaempferol and platinic chloride in highly acidic medium is completed at 28 equivalence resulting in the formation of formic acid as main oxidation product. The probable equation is

The presence of formic acid was confirmed by specific tests mentioned in the discussion.

Experimental

Reagents used : Kaempferol from the flowers of *Ipomoea fistulosa* (Indian grade); platinic chloride (Johnson Mathey & Co. Ltd. London grade); sulphuric acid, potassium ferrocyanide, ferrous ammonium sulphate, sodium carbonate (Analar, B.D.H. grade); ether (Alembic); ceric sulphate (Technical, B.D.H. grade); and N-phenylanthranilic acid (B.D.H. grade).

Apparatus used : Micropipettes and micro-burette with least count = 0.01 ml. Hot plate.

Purified sample of kaempferol was carefully weighed and dissolved in 0.001 N NaOH solution. Platinic chloride solution was prepared by dissolving in water which was further standardised⁴ by back titration method.

0.0032 N ceric sulphate (in 4N H_2SO_4) solution was standardised against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate (in 0.1N H_2SO_4) solution using N-phenylanthranilic acid solution as indicator.

0.0105 M potassium ferrocyanide solution was prepared in distilled water and was further standardised against 0.0032N ceric sulphate (in 4N H_2SO_4) solution using the above mentioned indicator.

0.1 g N-phenylanthranilic acid with 0.2 g Na_2CO_3 was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water.

Known volume of standard kaempferol solution was taken, through micropipette, in different beakers. Excess of standard platinic chloride solution was added to each beaker along with a known excess of standard sulphuric acid. After adding 30 ml distilled water to each beaker, they were put on a hot plate at full heat for 180 minutes (keeping in mind that the reaction mixture may not evaporate). In case the reaction mixture reduces to 5 or 10 ml in volume (much before 180 minutes) then 30 ml distilled water was more added. After cooling the reaction mixture at room temperature known excess of potassium ferrocyanide was added. Remaining potassium ferrocyanide was titrated against standard ceric sulphate (in 4N H_2SO_4) solution using N-phenylanthranilic acid solution as

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TABLE I—MICRODETERMINATION OF KAEMPFEROL

Kaempferol 0.0001M ml	H ₂ SO ₄ 9N ml	H ₂ PtCl ₆ 0.0029M ml	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ 0.0105M ml	Ce(SO ₄) ₂ 0.0032 N ml	Ce(SO ₄) ₂ 0.0032 N consumed ml	Amount of Kaempferol		Error %
						Taken × 10 ⁻³ mg	Found mg	
—	—	—	2	6.44	—	—	—	—
—	—	2	2	5.24	1.20	—	—	—
0.2	4	2	2	5.40	0.16	5.72	5.67	-0.8
0.3	4	2	2	5.50	0.26	8.58	8.49	-0.9
0.4	4	2	2	5.59	0.35	11.44	11.44	0.0
0.5	4	2	2	5.68	0.44	14.30	14.37	+0.4

indicator. At the end point reddish brown color appears sharply. Thus, by such back titration the value of the consumed platonic chloride was known which corresponds to the kaempferol oxidised.

Results and Discussion

Results are given in Table 1. The range in which kaempferol has been estimated varies from 5.67×10^{-3} to 14.37×10^{-3} mg.

Results show that the oxidation of kaempferol with platonic chloride in acid medium required 14 oxygen atoms and the rupture of the molecule resulted in the formation of formic acid as main oxidation product.

The reaction mixture was repeatedly extracted with ether (Alembic), washed and then the ethereal extract was shaken with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. Sodium bicarbonate extract was acidified and extracted with ether. Ether extract was washed till free from sulphate ions and then concentrated. The concentrate gave the test for formic acid, the identity of which was confirmed by co-chromatography on paper.

Since the reaction between kaempferol and platonic chloride in acid medium was completed at 28 equivalence, so calculations have been done by dividing the observed experimental values by 28. Maximum error in the present set of experiments has been observed as $\pm 0.9\%$. It is observed that the equilibrium is disturbed either by heating directly on the flame or by adding acid of much a lower concentration. However, the method is simple, accurate and reproducible.

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References

1. Y. OSHIMA, M. KIKUTANI and K. UMEMA, *J. Agr. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1953, 27, 98.
2. L. HORHAMMER and H. WAGNER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1956, 289, 532.
3. S. A. I. RIZVI and O. C. SAXENA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 255, 133.
4. O. C. SAXENA, *Talanta*, 1966, 13, 861.